

Environmentally green syntheses of Biginelli compounds, some fused and spiro-fused analogues and bis(indolyl)methanes[†]

Amarendra Patra* and Tanusri Mahapatra

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, University College of Science and Technology,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : amarendra.patra@gmail.com Fax : 91-33-23519755

Manuscript received 15 May 2013, accepted 07 January 2014

Abstract : One-pot synthesis of various known and new 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones/thiones, 5-oxooctahydroquinazolin-2-ones/thiones and spiro-fused heterocycles are reported using Aliquat[®]336 as a phase-transfer catalyst under microwave irradiation in water. This new method provides comparatively better catalyst for both Biginelli and Biginelli-like cyclocondensation, greener and milder reaction conditions, quicker reaction, simpler isolation of products and better yields. Catalysing efficiency of Aliquat[®]336 in conjunction with (NH₄)₂SO₄ was also tested for one pot two-component condensation of aldehydes and indole yielding various bis(indolyl)methanes in excellent yield under conventional heating.

Keywords : One-pot synthesis, dihydropyrimidinones, fused and spiro analogues, bis(indolyl)methanes, Aliquat[®]336, ammonium sulphate.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds particularly those are *N*-containing¹⁻⁵ have application as common structural motif used to develop compounds of biological or medicinal interest to synthetic chemists. Biginelli^{6,7} and Biginelli-like cyclocondensation reactions⁸⁻¹³ provide a well-studied route to the construction of *N*-containing heterocyclic compounds of comprehensive biological and pharmacological activities. It has been examined that several 3,4-dihydropyrimidinone derivatives can be active as calcium channel modulators¹⁴, anti-bacterial, antiinflammatory^{15,16}, antihypertensive agents and α -1*a*-antagonists¹⁷. Several alkaloids of marine origin constituted with 3,4-dihydropyrimidinone core have also been found to exhibit interesting biological activities. Most notably among these are the crambine and batzelladine alkaloids and the more complex ptilomycalin A. The batzelladine alkaloids are potent HIV gp-120-CD4 inhibitors¹⁸. Hence the classical Biginelli and Biginelli-like cyclocondensation reaction found rapid expansion and advancement through the involvement of newer alternate catalytic systems and synthetic strategies¹⁹⁻²⁷. Nevertheless, for the growing in-

terest in this class of compounds Biginelli and Biginelli-like cyclocondensation reactions are still being pursued today²⁸⁻³³ and search for newer catalytic system with efficient and advantageous procedures is of immense interest.

Based on our previous studies³⁴⁻³⁶, we have preferentially selected Aliquat[®]336 as the catalyst. It is commercially available, inexpensive, stable, non-hazardous, active under microwave condition and can be used without any pretreatment. It is an effective phase-transfer catalyst and has catalyzed successfully a large number of chemical processes³⁷⁻³⁹.

In the present context, we describe a microwave-assisted environmentally benign one-pot Biginelli and Biginelli-like cyclocondensation approach for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones/thiones (Scheme 1), 5-oxooctahydroquinazolin-2-ones/thiones⁴⁰⁻⁴³ (Scheme 2) and tetraazaspirodecane/tetraone/thioxotetraazaspirodecane/triones⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ (Scheme 3) under the phase-transfer catalysis of Aliquat[®]336 in water. Indeed synthesis of those heterocycles under phase-transfer catalysis method is relatively few⁴⁹.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Indole moiety is featured in wide variety of pharmacologically and biologically active compounds⁵⁰⁻⁵². Among these, the substrates including bis(indolyl)methane fragment are widely recognized as bioactive metabolites of terrestrial and marine origin^{53,54} and hence reviewed in recent years too. Several catalytic systems have been successfully utilized which includes protic acids⁵⁵, Lewis acids^{56,57}, heterogeneous acidic catalyst⁵⁸ and reagents like iodine⁵⁹, NBS⁶⁰, KHSO_4 ⁶¹, $\text{NaHSO}_4 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ ⁶², LiClO_4 ⁶³, $\text{Dy}(\text{OTf})_3$ /ionic liquid⁶⁴ etc.⁶⁵⁻⁷¹. The prob-

lem of using acidic catalyst truly lies in the acid sensitivity of indole moiety leading to some polymeric waste and demanding of catalyst in excess due to trapping by indole nitrogen. In this context we have thus given much more attention on ionic liquid mediated synthesis of bis(indolyl)methanes. We have employed this time Aliquat[®]336 (10 mol %) in conjunction with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ at temperature 70–80 °C. Condensation involves indole and various aromatic aldehydes leading to desired products in excellent yield (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Results and discussion

To execute our approach for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidinones, we have chosen three component condensation of benzaldehyde (1 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (1 mmol) and urea (1 mmol) in presence of catalyst Aliquat®336 (1 mol %) in conjunction with 3–5 ml of water as a probe reaction. We observed that the catalyst ensures effective condensation and cyclisation leading to the desired product in good yield. To optimize the reaction parameters we have performed several test reactions tuning reactant to catalyst ratio, and time of irradiation at a definite power level and also studied the effect of catalyst in water/in absence of water. Our results (Table 1) indicated that an excellent balance between efficacy in yields and time profile was observed using 1 : 1 : 1 : 0.05

Table 1. Standardisation of the amount of Aliquat®336 for the optimization of yield of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones

No. of observations	Amount of catalyst used/ mol % (mol)	Isolated yield of product (1) (%)
1	1 (0.01)	80
2	5 (0.05)	95
3	10 (0.10)	97

mole ratios of benzaldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate, urea and catalyst in water. An increase in the amount of catalyst from 0.01 to 0.05 equiv appeared to be beneficial. Further increase in the quantity of catalyst did not result in notable improvement. The significant contribution of water towards yield improvement (Table 2) ensures phase-transfer catalysis of Aliquat®336 in truly neutral condition. We also found that the reaction could be safely completed (monitored by TLC) in water at 720 W within several minutes with excellent yield, while at higher power

Table 2. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones/thiones using Aliquat®336 (5 mol %) in water and in absence of water

Products	Time (min) ^a	Yield (%) ^a	Time (min) ^b	Yield (%) ^b
1	10	95	18	75
12	15	88	25	65
16	10	92	22	70
22	10	90	25	68

^aReaction carried out using Aliquat®336 in water.

^bReaction carried out using Aliquat®336 in absence of water.

level and prolonged irradiation product decomposition occurred. The use of solvent water makes this process not only greener and milder, but also inexpensive. Overall, the process well tolerates wide variety of substituents on aldehyde moiety, accommodates comfortably different 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds with urea/thiourea proving its scope and generality (Table 3). Presence of electron withdrawing group like nitro essentially reduces reaction time though yields are good to excellent irrespective of the nature of the substituents. In addition, the catalytic system can be easily recovered and recycled. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), reaction mixture obtained was titrated well with crushed ice and then filtered. The residue obtained was washed with little diethyl ether and after removal of ether the filtrate containing entire Aliquat®336 was reused for the next 2–3 runs with little loss in catalytic activity (Table 4).

With the aim to further widen the applicability of the procedure, we took this time a cyclic 1,3-diketone like dimedone instead of open chain analogue and subjected to microwave irradiation under identical condition. We were pleased to note that this time also catalytic activity of Aliquat®336 enabled us to synthesize few 5-oxooctahydroquinazolin-2-ones/thiones (Table 5) in very good yield (80–85%).

Inspired by this observation this green catalytic system has been successfully extended to the synthesis of otherwise scanty tetraazaspirooundecanetetraones/thioxotetraazaspirooundecanetriones (Scheme 3). We have employed this time barbituric acid instead of dimedone along with aldehyde and urea/thiourea resulting in the formation of few selective tetraazaspiroheterocycles (Table 6) in reasonable yields (70–75%). However, when we employed the aforementioned catalytic condition for the aldehydes 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde and 2,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde the expected transformation did not occur; instead, it furnished only Knoevenagel condensation product in good yield (Fig. 1). From a comparison of the spectroscopic data of products **37–39** with that of the compounds reported in the literature^{44,47,48}, the configurations for the chiral carbons C-7 and C-11 have been assigned as *S**,*R** (7*S*,11*R*).

Table 3. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(*IH*)-ones/thiones using Aliquat®336 in water

Entry	Ar	X	R ² (Reactant)	Products	Time (min)	Yields ^a (%)	m.p. (°C)	
							Found	Reported
1	C ₆ H ₅	O	CO ₂ Et	1	10	95	201–203	202–204 ⁷⁴
2	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	2	8	95	224–226	225–227 ⁷⁴
3	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	3	8	92	208–209	208–210 ⁷⁴
4	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	4	10	96	214–216	215–216 ⁷⁴
5	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	5	15	88	201–203	200–202 ⁷⁴
6	4-NMe ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	6	14	80	255–257	256–258 ⁷⁵
7	4-OH-3-OMeC ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Et	7	15	82	231–233	231–232 ⁷⁵
8	3-OBn-4-OMeC ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Et	8^b	12	84	154–156
9	4-OBnC ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Et	9^b	13	80	152–154
10	2-Br-4,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂	O	CO ₂ Et	10^b	15	80	192–194
11	3,4-(O-CH ₂ -O)C ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Et	11	12	80	187–189	188–189 ⁷⁵
12	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	O	CO ₂ Et	12	15	88	236–239	237–239 ⁷⁴
13	Furyl	O	CO ₂ Et	13	12	87	201–203	202–204 ⁷⁵
14	CH ₃ CH ₂	O	CO ₂ Et	14	10	80	171–173	170–172 ⁷⁵
15	CH ₃ CH ₂	O	CO ₂ Me	15	13	90	185–186	184–186 ⁷⁵
16	C ₆ H ₅	O	CO ₂ Me	16	10	92	210–212	209–211 ⁷⁵
17	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Me	17	12	83	192–193	192–194 ⁷⁵
18	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	CO ₂ Me	18	8	85	282–283	280–282 ⁷⁷
19	4-OH-3-OMeC ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Me	19	18	80	220–221	220–222 ⁷⁵
20	3,4-(O-CH ₂ -O)C ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Me	20	15	80	195–197	196–198 ²⁸
21	3,4-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	O	CO ₂ Me	21	15	82	151–153	150–152 ⁷⁵
22	3,4-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	S	CO ₂ Et	22	10	90	150–152	152–153 ⁷⁸
23	3-OMeC ₆ H ₄	S	CO ₂ Et	23	10	84	151–153	150–152 ⁷⁶
24	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	S	CO ₂ Et	24	12	90	140–142	141–143 ⁴⁹
25	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	S	CO ₂ Et	25	8	90	208–209	208–210 ⁷⁹
26	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	S	CO ₂ Et	26	5	98	202–204	203–205 ⁸⁰
27	CH ₃ CH ₂	S	CO ₂ Et	27	7	85	147–148	148–149 ⁸¹
28	C ₆ H ₅	S	CO ₂ Et	28	6	95	205–206	205–207 ³¹
29	C ₆ H ₅	S	COMe	29	5	98	220–222	219–221 ⁷⁴
30	C ₆ H ₅	O	COMe	30	10	98	233–236	232–235 ¹⁰
31	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	CN	31^b	7	95	262

^aIsolated yields. ^bNewly synthesized compounds.**Table 4.** Results of recycling study

No. of cycles	Amount of catalyst used (mol %)	Isolated yield of product 1 (%)
1	5	95
2	5	94
3	5	92

In case of synthesis of bis(indolyl)methanes we have performed the test reaction involving benzaldehyde (1 mmol) and indole (2 mmol) with Aliquat®336 (10 mol %)

in room temperature under stirring for 1 h but without result. The same reaction when performed in oil bath at temperature 70–80 °C furnished the desired bis(indolyl)-methane within 30 min in good yield. We have then repeated the aforementioned reaction with Aliquat®336 (10 mol %) in conjunction with (NH₄)₂SO₄ (0.1 mmol) under identical condition (Scheme 4). We observed that this time the reaction was complete within 20 min (monitored by TLC) providing the expected bis(indolyl)methane derivative in good yield. However, the same reaction when

Table 5. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 5-oxooctahydroquinazolin-2-ones/thiones using Aliquat®336 in water

Entry	Ar	X	Products	Time (min)	Yields (%)	m.p. (°C)	
						Found	Reported
1	C ₆ H ₅	O	32	10	82	293–294	292–295 ⁴³
2	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	O	33	17	80	227–229	229 ⁴²
3	4-HOC ₆ H ₄	O	34	15	85	301–303	300–302 ⁴³
4	2,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	S	35^b	20	83	150–152
5	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	S	36^b	18	85	176–178

^aIsolated yields. ^bNewly synthesized compounds.

Table 6. Microwave-assisted synthesis of tetraazaspiroindecanetetraone/thioxotetraazaspiroindecanetriones using Aliquat®336 in water

Entry	Ar	X	Products	Time (min)	Yields (%)	m.p. (°C)	
						Found	Reported
1	C ₆ H ₅	O	37	20	70	240–242	240–241 ⁴⁷
2	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	O	38	12	72	220–223	222–224 ⁴⁸
3	C ₆ H ₅	S	39	15	75	246–248	245–247 ⁴⁴

^aIsolated yield.

Fig. 1

carried out at room temperature with (NH₄)₂SO₄ (1 mmol) in DCM solvent did not furnish expected product even after 2 h of stirring. Also the same reaction with (NH₄)₂SO₄ (1 mmol) under solvent-free condition at temperature 70–80 °C failed to afford the expected product. It is worth mentioning that Aliquat®336 being room temperature ionic liquid here exhibited dual solvent-catalyst^{72–74} activity and it is further manifested by (NH₄)₂SO₄ as promoter. However, this method was found to be fruitful for aromatic aldehydes only. In this method ketones were tested to be non-responsive.

All the products were well characterized by spectroscopic studies. Newly synthesized compounds were further confirmed in few cases by HRMS studies and physical and spectroscopic data of known compounds obtained were compared with the reported data of authentic samples. Thus for active methylene compound viz. 2-cyanoacetamide,

selective formation of **31** instead of **31'** (Fig. 2) has been ascertained as follows : compound **31** showed molecular ion peak (M⁺) at *m/z* 277.0812 in QTOF MS in conformity with its molecular formula C₁₁H₁₁N₅O₄ instead of C₁₁H₉N₅O₃. The appearance of two distinct bands viz. at 1702 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum were attributed to be two types of amide carbonyls viz. at 2- and 7-positions respectively. Absence of an IR absorption band at ~2190 cm⁻¹ clearly obliterated the presence of conjugated CN moiety in the product. The ¹H NMR spectrum displayed resonances for eleven protons confirming involvement of three-component moieties in the resulting product and again in consonance with the structure **31** instead of **31'**. Presence of a signal at δ 5.33 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz) with small coupling constant has been assigned to methine proton at C-4 due to its coupling with adjacent NH₍₃₎ resonance at δ 7.64 (br. s) (established by COSY experiment). The appearance of another broad singlet sig-

Fig. 2

nal in the more downfield region (δ 8.71) that has been easily assigned to $\text{NH}_{(1)}$ resonance is also in conformity with its environment. A hump like appearance of two singlet signals at δ 6.90 and 7.08 confirmed the presence of $-\text{CONH}_2$ moiety in the resulting product. Signal for 6-NH_2 superimposed with that of $\text{NH}_{(3)}$ and appeared as br. s at δ 7.64. The appearance of downfield signals at δ 8.05 (1H, br. s) and 8.09 (1H, dd, J 7.8 Hz, 1.7 Hz) in consonance with the signals for two protons *ortho* to nitro group ($2'\text{-H}$ and $4'\text{-H}$ respectively). The splitting pattern of the signal at δ 7.65 (1H, dd, J 7.7 Hz, 1.6 Hz) conforms to proton *para* to nitro group ($6'\text{-H}$) whereas that for the signal at δ 7.60 (1H, dd, J 7.7 Hz, 7.7 Hz) attributed to proton *meta* to nitro group ($5'\text{-H}$). All these data are in conformity with the presence of a *meta*-nitrophenyl moiety in the product.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra together with DEPT-135 experiment for **31** provided evidence for the presence of eleven constituent carbons of which five were protonated and six quaternary. Two-dimensional HSQC experiment was performed to identify a protonated carbon signal through correlation with the corresponding proton signal. Thus resonances at δ_c 54.5, 121.5, 122.7, 130.5 and 133.5 have been assigned to protonated carbons C-4, C-2', C-4', C-5' and C-6', respectively, of **31**. Identification of the non-protonated carbon resonances were made, however, from HMBC experiment performed. Here 4-H signal exhibited multiple bond correlation with carbon resonances at δ 104.0 (C-5), 121.5 (C-2'), 133.5 (C-6'), 140.2 (C-1'), 146.7 (C-6), 152.8 (C-2) and 168.5 (CONH_2). Also ^1H resonances for $2'\text{-H}$ exhibited multiple bond correlation with carbon resonances at δ 54.5 (C-4), 122.7 (C-4'), 133.5 (C-6'), 148.1 (C-3') while $6'\text{-H}$ had correlation with carbon signals at 121.5 (C-2'), 122.7 (C-4'), 54.5 (C-4). Thus, resonances for protonated carbons C-2' and C-6' were verified which in turn sorted out protonated C-4' resonance too. Hence residual protonated carbon resonance at δ 130.5 was for C-5'. Again, ^1H NMR resonances for $\text{NH}_{(1)}$, $\text{NH}_{(3)}$ and 6-NH_2 showed correlations with non-protonated carbon resonance at δ 104.0. ^1H resonance for 6-NH_2 also showed correlation with non-protonated carbon resonance at δ 146.7 and that for $4'\text{-H}$ and $5'\text{-H}$ showed correlation with non-protonated

carbon resonance at δ 148.1. Thus, the carbon resonances at δ 104.0, 146.7 and 148.1 were identified for C-5, C-6 and C-3', respectively. HMBC experiment, however, did not provide clue to establish the association of non-protonated carbon resonances at δ 152.8 and 168.5 specifically. Chemical environment supports C-2 resonating upfield at δ 152.8 by being flanked by two electron donating NH (by conjugation) and thus, δ 168.5 resonance is assignable to 5-CONH_2 . ^{13}C NMR and DEPT-135 experiments together again obviate any quaternary carbon resonance for nitrile carbon at $\sim \delta$ 120.0. Multiple bond correlations for **31** are depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

In conclusion, we have reported a practical, green and versatile synthetic method which allows the facile synthesis of a broad range of functional heterocyclic compounds such as 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones/thiones, 5-oxooctahydroquinazolin-2-ones/thiones, tetraazaspiroundecanetetraone/thioxotetraazaspiroundecanetriones, and bis(indolyl)methanes. The merits of this methodology include simplicity in operation, easier enough work up procedure and utility of a single substance Aliquat[®]336 as phase-transfer catalyst in one hand and ionic liquid in the other having dual solvent-catalyst activity in either purely neutral condition or in almost neutral condition under two different modes of heating.

Experimental

Melting points (uncorrected) were recorded on a Toshniwal apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on a

Table 7. Conventional synthesis of bis(indolyl)methanes

Entry	Ar	Products	Time ^a (min)	Yields ^a (%)	Time ^b (min)	Yields ^b (%)	m.p. (°C)	
							Found	Reported
1	C ₆ H ₅	40	20	70	30	55	123–126	124–125 ⁶⁵
2	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	41	18	75	25	60	139–141	140–141 ⁶⁷
3	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	42	15	80	25	65	221–224	220–222 ⁶⁸
4	3-OHC ₆ H ₄	43	18	78	30	60	100–102	101–103 ⁶⁶
5	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	44	22	72	35	58	124–125	125–126 ⁶⁹
6	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	45	25	70	40	55	121–122	120–122 ⁷⁰
7	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	46	25	75	35	60	113–114	112–113 ⁷¹
8	4-OH-3,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂	47 ^{c,82}	30	65	45	50	200–202
9	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	48 ^{c,83}	30	70	40	55	188–190

^aReaction carried out using Aliquat®336/(NH₄)₂SO₄.

^bReaction carried out using Aliquat®336 in absence of (NH₄)₂SO₄.

^cM.p. not found in the literature available.

Perkin-Elmer FT IR-RXI spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ¹H (300 MHz) and ¹³C (75 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV 300 supercon NMR spectrometer in 5 mm BBO probe in *d*₆-DMSO (for products **1-34**, **37-39**)/CDCl₃ as solvent (for products **35**, **36**, **40-48**) and mass spectra on a Qtof Micro YA 263 spectrometer. Multiplicity of the signals was determined by DEPT-135 experiment and specific ¹³C NMR signal assignments of the products were done using HSQC and HMBC experiments.

General procedure for the products **1-39** :

A mixture of aldehyde (1 mmol; for products **37-39**, 2 mmol), active methylene compound (1 mmol), urea/thiourea (1 mmol) and Aliquat®336 (5 mol %) in water (3–5 ml) taken in an Erlenmeyer flask (25 ml) fitted with a loose top containing crushed ice inside was placed inside a BPL-SANYO, 700T domestic microwave oven and irradiated at 720 W until spots for aldehyde and active methylene compound almost disappeared in TLC (Table 1). The content after the reaction was stirred with crushed ice and the solid separated out filtered, washed with little diethyl ether and crystallised from dichloromethane-ethanol mixture.

General procedure for the products **40-48** :

A mixture of indole (2 mmol), aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol), Aliquat®336 (10 mol %) and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (0.1 mmol) taken in a conical flask was heated in an oil bath at 70–80 °C for 15–30 min. The reaction mixture turned

reddish pink within few minutes. The reaction was monitored by TLC until spot for aldehyde almost disappeared. After completion of reaction, the content was leached with 10–15 ml dichloromethane and the organic layer kept overnight over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator and the resultant mass obtained was purified by column chromatography [for compounds **40-42**, 5% EtOAc-petrol ether (P.E.) mixture as eluant] and preparative TLC [for compounds **43** and **44**, EtOAc : P.E. (25 : 75, v/v); **45** and **46**, EtOAc : P.E. (15 : 85, v/v); **47**, EtOAc : P.E. (30 : 70, v/v) and **48**, EtOAc : P.E. (40 : 60, v/v) as eluant].

Spectral data of selected products :

4-(3-Benzyloxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(ethoxycarbonyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (**8**) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3364, 3242, 1696, 1646, 737, 696; δ_{H} : 1.05 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.19 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 3.69 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 3.92 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.97 (2H, s, OCH₂Ph), 5.04 (1H, d, *J* 2.9 Hz, 4-H), 6.71 (1H, dd, *J* 8.3 Hz and 1.7 Hz, 6'-H), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 5'-H), 6.89 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.29–7.40 (5H, complex m, 2'', 3'', 4'', 5'', 6''-H), 7.62 (1H, s, NH₍₃₎), 9.10 (1H, s, NH₍₁₎); δ_{C} : 14.2 (OCH₂CH₃), 17.8 (6-CH₃), 53.5 (C-4), 55.7 (4'-OCH₃), 59.2 (OCH₂CH₃), 70.2 (OCH₂Ph), 99.4 (C-5), 112.1 (C-2'), 112.4 (C-5'), 118.7 (C-6'), 127.7 (C-4''), 127.9 (C-6''), 128.5 (C-5''), 137.1 (C-1''), 137.4 (C-1'), 147.6 (C-3'), 148.2 (C-6), 148.6 (C-4'), 152.3 (C-2), 165.5 (CO₂CH₂CH₃); *m/z*, M⁺ (%), Found : 397.1756

(100). Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_5$: 397.1758.

4-(4-Benzyloxyphenyl)-5-(ethoxycarbonyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (9) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3245, 3114, 1703, 1647, 738, 697; δ_H : 1.05 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.20 (3H, s, 6- CH_3), 3.94 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 5.03 (2H, s, OCH_2Ph), 5.05 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz, 4-H), 6.91 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, 3'-H, 5'-H), 7.11 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, 2'-H, 6'-H), 7.27–7.40 (5H, m, 2'', 3'', 4'', 5'', 6''-H), 7.63 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(3)}$), 9.11 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(1)}$); δ_C : 14.2 (OCH_2CH_3), 17.8 (6- CH_3), 53.4 (C-4), 59.2 (OCH_2CH_3), 69.3 (OCH_2Ph), 99.6 (C-5), 114.7 (C-3', C-5'), 127.5 (C-2', C-6'), 127.7 (C-2'', C-6''), 127.9 (C-4''), 128.5 (C-3'', C-5''), 137.2 (C-1''), 137.4 (C-1'), 148.1 (C-6), 152.2 (C-2), 157.6 (C-4'); m/z , M^+ (%), Found : 367.1652 (100). Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_4$: 367.1652.

4-(2-Bromo-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-5-(ethoxycarbonyl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (10) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3331, 3228, 1700, 1650; δ_H : 0.96 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.22 (3H, s, 5- CH_3), 3.90 (2H, m, OCH_2CH_3), 3.65 (3H, s, 4'- OCH_3), 3.68 (3H, s, 5'- OCH_3), 5.45 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, 4-H), 6.71 (1H, s, 3'-H), 7.01 (1H, s, 6'-H), 7.50 (1H, s, $NH_{(3)}$), 9.09 (1H, s, $NH_{(1)}$); δ_C : 14.5 (CH_3), 18.1 (6- CH_3), 54.7 (C-4), 56.2 (4'- OCH_3), 56.5 (5'- OCH_3), 59.9 (OCH_2), 99.2 (C-5), 112.0 (C-3'), 112.8 (C-2'), 116.1 (C-6'), 135.5 (C-1'), 149.1 (C-6), 149.4 (C-4'), 149.5 (C-5'), 152.2 (C-2), 165.8 ($CO_2CH_2CH_3$); m/z , M^+ (%), Found : 399.0553 (100, for Br^{79}), 401.0574 (88, for Br^{81}). Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{19}N_2O_5Br$: 399.0550 (for Br^{79}), 401.0532 (for Br^{81}).

6-Amino-5-carboxamido-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (31) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3369, 3198, 1702, 1600, 1528, 733; δ_H : 5.33 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, 4-H), 6.90 (1H, s, $CONH_a$), 7.08 (1H, s, $CONH_b$), 7.60 (1H, dd, J 7.7 Hz, 7.7 Hz, 5'-H), 7.64 (3H, br. s, $NH_{(3)}$ + 6- NH_2), 7.65 (1H, dd, J 7.7 Hz, 1.6 Hz, 6'-H), 8.05 (1H, br. s, 2'-H), 8.09 (1H, dd, J 7.8 Hz, 1.7 Hz, 4'-H), 8.71 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(1)}$); δ_C : 54.5 (C-4, $^1J_{C-H}$ 144.7 Hz), 104.0 (C-5), 121.5 (C-2', $^1J_{C-H}$ 166.3 Hz), 122.7 (C-4', $^1J_{C-H}$ 172.0 Hz), 130.5 (C-5', $^1J_{C-H}$ 166.7 Hz), 133.5 (C-6', $^1J_{C-H}$ 162.0 Hz, $^2J_{C-H}$ 3.8 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.7 Hz), 140.2 (C-1', $^2J_{C-H}$ 5.5 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.1 Hz), 146.7 (C-6, $^3J_{C-H}$ 3.7 Hz), 148.1 (C-3', $^2J_{C-H}$ 3.1 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.2 Hz), 152.8 (C-2, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.1 Hz), 168.5 ($CONH_2$); m/z ,

M^+ (%), Found : 276.9543 (20). Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{11}N_5O_4$: 277.0811.

7,7-Dimethyl-4-(2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolin-2-thione (35) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3384, 1722, 1609; δ_H : 1.10 (6H, br. s, 7- $CH_{3(a)}$, 7- $CH_{3(b)}$), 2.34 (4H, br. s, 6- H_a , 6- H_b , 8- H_a , 8- H_b), 3.67 (3H, s, 2'- OCH_3), 3.73 (3H, s, 5'- OCH_3), 4.80 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(3)}$), 5.53 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.70 (2H, s, 3'-H, 4'-H), 6.82 (1H, s, 6'-H), 11.83 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(1)}$); δ_C : 26.9 (7- $CH_{3(a)}$, 7- $CH_{3(b)}$), $^1J_{C-H}$ 126.8 Hz), 29.4 (C-4, $^1J_{C-H}$ 127.2 Hz), 31.2 (C-7), 46.7 (C-6, C-8, $^1J_{C-H}$ 127.2 Hz), 55.6 (2'- OCH_3 , $^1J_{C-H}$ 143.2 Hz), 55.7 (5'- OCH_3 , $^1J_{C-H}$ 143.4 Hz), 110.8 (C-4', $^1J_{C-H}$ 158.5 Hz), 111.2 (C-3', $^1J_{C-H}$ 160.1 Hz, $^2J_{C-H}$ 5.6 Hz), 115.8 (C-6', $^1J_{C-H}$ 155.8 Hz), 116.3 (C-4a), 128.0 (C-1'), 151.4 (C-2', C-8a), 153.0 (C-5'), 189.1 (C-2, C-5, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.2 Hz); m/z , M^+ gly (%), Found : 437.9135 (10). Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{30}N_2O_6S$: 438.1825.

7,7-Dimethyl-4-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolin-2-thione (36) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3380, 1720, 1610; δ_H : 1.12 (3H, s, 7- $CH_{3(a)}$), 1.25 (3H, s, 7- $CH_{3(b)}$), 2.36 (2H, s, 8- CH_a , 8- CH_b), 2.39 (1H, d, J 18 Hz, 6- CH_a), 2.46 (1H, d, J 18 Hz, 6- CH_b), 3.75 (6H, s, 3'- OCH_3 , 5'- OCH_3), 3.82 (3H, s, 4'- OCH_3), 4.80 (1H, br. s, $NH_{(3)}$), 5.50 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.35 (2H, s, 2'-H, 6'-H), 12.0 (1H, s, $NH_{(1)}$); δ_C : 26.7 (7- $CH_{3(a)}$, $^1J_{C-H}$ 126.9 Hz), 29.9 (7- $CH_{3(b)}$, $^1J_{C-H}$ 124.1 Hz), 31.0 (C-7, $^2J_{C-H}$ 3.5 Hz, 3.8 Hz), 32.7 (C-4, $^1J_{C-H}$ 122.4 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 4.4 Hz), 46.3 (C-8, $^1J_{C-H}$ 128.2 Hz), 47.0 (C-6, $^1J_{C-H}$ 126.8 Hz), 55.8 (3'- OCH_3 , 5'- OCH_3 , $^1J_{C-H}$ 144.0 Hz), 60.8 (4'- OCH_3 , $^1J_{C-H}$ 144.3 Hz), 104.1 (C-2', C-6', $^1J_{C-H}$ 157.4 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.7 Hz), 115.5 (C-4a, $^2J_{C-H}$ 6.8 Hz), 133.7 (C-1', $^2J_{C-H}$ 9.5 Hz), 135.9 (C-4'), 152.8 (C-8a, C-3', C-5'), 189.2 (C-2), 190.3 (C-5).

7S,11R-Diphenyl-2,4,8,10-tetraazaspiro[5.5]undecane-1,3,5,9-tetraone (37) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3238, 3063, 1730, 1696; δ_H : 5.18 (2H, s, 7-H, 11-H), 7.11–7.16 (4H, m, 3'-H, 3''-H, 5'-H, 5''-H), 7.27–7.29 (6H, m, 2'-H, 2''-H, 4'-H, 4''-H, 6'-H, 6''-H), 9.91 (2H, br. s, 8-NH, 10-NH), 10.96 (1H, s, 4-NH), 11.34 (1H, s, 2-NH); δ_C : 57.2 (C-6), 61.3 (C-7, C-11, $^1J_{C-H}$ 148.2 Hz), 127.5 (C-3', C-3'', C-5', C-5'', $^1J_{C-H}$ 156.7 Hz), 128.6 (C-2', C-2'', C-6', C-6'', $^1J_{C-H}$ 164.9 Hz), 129.1 (C-4', C-4'', $^1J_{C-H}$ 161.6 Hz), 135.8 (C-1', C-1''), 148.8 (C-3), 150.9 (C-

9), 165.6 (C-1), 170.0 (C-5).

7S, 11R-Diphenyl-9-thioxo-2,4,8,10-tetraazaspiro-[5.5]undecane-1,3,5-trione (39) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3359, 3308, 1734, 1702; δ_{H} : 5.15 (2H, s, 7-H, 11-H), 7.09–7.12 (4H, m, 3'-H, 3''-H, 5'-H, 5''-H), 7.28–7.30 (6H, m, 2'-H, 2''-H, 4'-H, 4''-H, 6'-H, 6''-H), 8.75 (2H, br. s, 8-NH, 10-NH), 11.07 (1H, s, 4-NH), 11.46 (1H, s, 2-NH); δ_{C} : 55.6 (C-6), 61.3 (C-7, C-11, ¹J_{C-H} 153.6 Hz), 127.5 (C-3', C-3'', C-5', C-5'', ¹J_{C-H} 160.3 Hz), 128.5 (C-2', C-2'', C-6', C-6'', ¹J_{C-H} 159.7 Hz, ³J_{C-H} 5.1 Hz), 129.1 (C-4', C-4'', ¹J_{C-H} 161.2 Hz, ³J_{C-H} 7.0 Hz), 134.4 (C-1', C-1''), 148.5 (C-3), 165.4 (C-1), 169.6 (C-5), 177.3 (C-9).

3,3'-(4-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenylmethylene)-bis(1H-indole) (47) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3370, 3043, 1616, 1509, 1457, 1212, 1108, 742; δ_{H} : 3.76 (6H, s, 3''-OCH₃, 5''-OCH₃), 5.42 (1H, br. s, OH), 5.81 (1H, s, 8-H), 6.60 (2H, s, 2''-H, 6''-H), 6.66 (2H, s, 2-H, 2'-H), 7.01 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, 5-H, 5'-H), 7.17 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 6-H, 6'-H), 7.36 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 7-H, 7'-H), 7.41 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, 4-H, 4'-H), 7.93 (2H, br. s, 1-NH, 1'-NH); δ_{C} : 40.3 (C-8), 56.3 (3''-OCH₃, 5''-OCH₃), 105.6 (C-2'', C-6''), 111.0 (C-7, C-7'), 119.2 (C-5, C-5'), 119.8 (C-3, C-3'), 119.9 (C-4, C-4'), 121.9 (C-6, C-6'), 123.5 (C-2, C-2'), 127.1 (C-3a, C-3a'), 133.0 (C-4''), 135.3 (C-1''), 136.7 (C-7a, C-7a'), 146.9 (C-3'', C-5'').

3,3'-(3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenylmethylene)bis(1H-indole) (48) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3384, 1592, 1501, 1226, 1124, 742; δ_{H} : 3.72 (6H, s, 3''-OCH₃, 5''-OCH₃), 3.83 (3H, s, 4''-OCH₃), 5.82 (1H, s, 8-H), 6.60 (2H, s, 2''-H, 6''-H), 6.71 (2H, s, 2-H, 2'-H), 7.02 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 5-H, 5'-H), 7.17 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 6-H, 6'-H), 7.36 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 7-H, 7'-H), 7.42 (2H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, 4-H, 4'-H), 7.96 (2H, br. s, 1-NH, 1'-NH); δ_{C} : 40.6 (C-8), 56.1 (3''-OCH₃, 5''-OCH₃), 60.9 (4''-OCH₃), 105.9 (C-2'', C-6''), 111.0 (C-7, C-7'), 119.3 (C-5, C-5'), 119.9 (C-4, C-4'), 119.6 (C-3, C-3'), 122.0 (C-6, C-6'), 123.5 (C-2, C-2'), 127.1 (C-3a, C-3a'), 136.7 (C-7a, C-7a', C-4''), 139.8 (C-1''), 153.0 (C-3'', C-5'').

Acknowledgement

We thank the CAS Instrumentation Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, India for spectral data and the UGC, New Delhi and University of

Calcutta, Kolkata for financial assistance.

References

1. Y.-L. Chen, K.-C. Fang, J.-Y. Sheu, S.-L. Hsu and C.-C. Tzeng, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **44**, 2374.
2. P. M. S. Chauhan and S. K. Srivastava, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **8**, 1535.
3. M. Balasubramanian and J. G. Keay, in : "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry II", Vol. 5, eds. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, Pergamon Press, New York, 1996, pp. 245.
4. K. Faber, H. Stuckler and T. Kappe, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1984, **21**, 1177.
5. G. Kolokythas, N. Pouli, P. Marakos, H. Pratsinis and D. Kletsas, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **41**, 71.
6. P. Biginelli, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1893, **23**, 360.
7. K. Folkers, H. J. Harwood and T. B. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3751.
8. G. Byk, H. E. Gottlieb, J. Herscovici and F. Mirkin, *J. Comb. Chem.*, 2000, **2**, 732.
9. M. M. Abelman, S. C. Smith and D. R. James, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 4559.
10. A. Shaabani, A. Bazgir and F. Teimouri, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 857.
11. K. S. Atwal, B. C. O'Reilly, J. Z. Gougoutas and M. F. Malley, *Heterocycles*, 1987, **26**, 1189.
12. K. S. Atwal, G. C. Rovnyak, B. C. O'Reilly and J. Schwartz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 5898.
13. A. D. Shutalev and V. Kuksa, *Khim. Geterotsicl. Soedin.*, 1997, 105.
14. K. S. Atwal, B. N. Swanson, S. E. Unger, D. M. Floyd, S. Moreland, A. Hedberg and B. C. O'Reilly, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 806.
15. B. B. Snider and Z. Shi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 3828.
16. L. E. Overman, M. H. Rabinowitz and P. A. Renhowe, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 2657.
17. K. S. Atwal, G. C. Rovnyak, S. D. Kimball, D. M. Floyd, S. Moreland, B. N. Swanson, J. Z. Gougoutas, J. Schwartz, K. M. Smillie and M. F. Malley, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, **33**, 2629.
18. A. D. Patil, N. V. Kumar, W. C. Kokke, M. F. Bean, A. J. Freyer, C. De Brosse, S. Mai, A. Truneh, D. J. Faulkner, B. Carte, A. L. Breen, R. P. Hertzberg, R. K. Johnson, J. W. Westley and B. C. M. Potts, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 1182.
19. E. H. Hu, D. R. Sidler and U.-H. Dolling, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 3454.
20. J. Lu and H. R. Ma, *Synlett*, 2000, 63.
21. Y. Ma, C. Qian, L. Wang and M. Yang, *J. Org.*

- Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 3864.
22. J. S. Yadav, B. V. S. Reddy, R. Srinivas, C. Venugopal and T. Ramalingam, *Synthesis*, 2001, 1341.
 23. J. Lu, Y. Bai, Z. Wang, B. Yang and H. Ma, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **41**, 9075.
 24. B. C. Ranu, A. Hajra and U. Jana, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 6270.
 25. R. Varala, M. M. Alam and S. R. Adapa, *Synlett*, 2003, 67.
 26. S. L. Jain, V. B. Sharma and B. Sain, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2006, **43**, 777.
 27. X. Chen and Y. Peng, *Catal. Lett.*, 2008, **122**, 310.
 28. M. Lei, D.-D. Wu, H.-G. Wei and Y.-G. Wang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2009, **39**, 475.
 29. H. Murata, H. Ishitani and M. Iwamoto, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2010, **8**, 1202.
 30. S. Chitra, D. Devanathan and K. Pandiarajan, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 367.
 31. H. R. Shaterian, A. Hosseinian, M. Ghashang, F. Khorami and N. Karimpour, *Phosphorus, Sulfur Silicon Relat. Elem.*, 2009, **184**, 2333.
 32. K. K. Pasunooti, H. Chai, C. N. Jensen, B. K. Gorityala, S. Wang and X.-W. Liu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 80.
 33. R. N. Bhattacharya, P. Kundu and G. Maiti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 26.
 34. A. Patra and T. Mahapatra, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2005, 629; 2008, 405; 2010, 689.
 35. A. Patra and T. Mahapatra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 925.
 36. A. Patra and T. Mahapatra, *Synth. Commun.*, 2013, **43**, 1602.
 37. H. X. Yu, B. K.-W. Man, L. L.-N. Chan, M. H.-W. Lam, P. K. S. Lam, L. Wang, H. Jin and R. S. S. Wu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **509**, 63.
 38. G. Kyuchoukov, M. Marinova, J. Albet and J. Molinier, *Indust. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2004, **43**, 1179.
 39. C. Villa, E. Mariani, A. Loupy, C. Grippo, G. C. Grossi and A. Bargagna, *Green Chem.*, 2003, **5**, 623.
 40. S. Sarac, M. Yarim, M. Ertan, S. Boydag and K. Erol, *Pharmazie*, 1998, **53**, 91.
 41. S. Sarac, M. Yarim, M. Ertan, F. S. Kilic and K. Erol, *Pharmazie*, 2001, **56**, 298.
 42. P. Shanmugam, C. Sabastein and P. T. Perumal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 135.
 43. S. Kantevari, R. Bantu and L. Nagarapu, *Arkivoc*, 2006, xvi, 136.
 44. V. P. Borovik and V. P. Mamaev, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1970, **4**, 32.
 45. A. Shaabani, A. Bazgir and H. R. Bijanzadeh, *Mol. Diversity*, 2004, **8**, 141.
 46. A. Shaabani and A. Bazgir, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 2575.
 47. M. M. Amini, A. Shaabani and A. Bazgir, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 843.
 48. J. L. Mokrosz, M. H. Paluchowska, E. Szneler and B. Drozd, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1989, **322**, 321.
 49. B. Ahmed, R. A. Khan, Habibullah and M. Keshari, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 2889.
 50. R. J. Sundberg, "The Chemistry of Indoles", Academic Press, New York, 1996, pp. 113.
 51. M. Sakagami, H. Muratake and M. Natsume, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1994, **42**, 1393.
 52. T. Fukuyama and X. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 3125.
 53. T. Osawa and M. Namiki, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 4719.
 54. G. Bifulco, I. Bruno, R. Riccio, J. Lavayre and G. Bourdy, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1995, **58**, 1254.
 55. B. P. Bandgar and K. A. Shaikh, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 1959.
 56. G. Babu, N. Sridhar and P. T. Perumal, *Synth. Commun.*, 2000, **30**, 1609.
 57. R. Nagarajan and P. T. Perumal, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 1229.
 58. M. Chakrabarty, N. Ghosh, R. Basak and Y. Harigaya, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 4075.
 59. S. J. Ji, S. Y. Wang, Y. Zhang and T.-P. Loh, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, **60**, 2051.
 60. H. Koshima and W. Matsuoka, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2002, **39**, 1089.
 61. R. Nagarajan and P. T. Perumal, *Chem. Lett.*, 2004, **33**, 288.
 62. C. Ramesh, J. Benerjee, R. Pal and B. Das, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2003, **345**, 557.
 63. J. S. Yadav, B. V. Subba Reddy, Ch. V. S. R. Murthy, G. M. Kumar and Ch. Madan, *Synthesis*, 2001, 783.
 64. X. Mi, S. Luo, J. He and J.-P. Cheng, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 4567.
 65. R. Ghorbani-Vaghei, H. Veisi, H. Keypour and A. A. Dehghani-Firouzabadi, *Mol. Diversity*, 2010, **14**, 87.
 66. Z.-H. Zhang, L. Yin and Y.-M. Wang, *Synthesis*, 2005, 1949.
 67. Y.-Y. Peng, Q.-L. Zhang, J.-J. Yuan and J.-P. Cheng, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 2008, **26**, 2228.
 68. A. Hasaninejad, A. Zare, H. Sharghi, M. Shekouhy, R. Khalifeh, A. S. Beni and A. R. M. Zare, *Can. J. Chem.*, 2007, **85**, 416.
 69. S. S. Sonar, S. A. Sadaphal, A. H. Kategaonkar, R. U. Pokalwar, B. B. Shingate and M. S. Shingare,

Patra *et al.* : Environmentally green syntheses of Biginelli compounds, some fused and spiro-fused *etc.*

- Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **30**, 825.
70. S. A. Sadaphal, S. S. Sonar, M. N. Ware and M. S. Shingare, *Green Chem. Lett. Rev.*, 2008, **1**, 191.
71. F. Shirini, M. S. Langroodi and M. Abedini, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **21**, 1342.
72. B. C. Ranu, S. Banerjee and R. Jana, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 776.
73. B. C. Ranu, S. Banerjee and A. Das, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 881.
74. W. Pei and Q. Wang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2010, **40**, 1209.
75. A. K. Mitra and K. Banerjee, *Synlett*, 2003, 1509.
76. H. Khabazzadeh, K. Saidi and H. Sheibani, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 278.
77. S. Tu, F. Fang, S. Zhu, T. Li, X. Zhang and Q. Zhuang, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2004, **41**, 253.
78. R. Gupta, A. K. Gupta, S. Paul and P. L. Kachroo, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **34**, 151.
79. L. Wang and C. Cai, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2008, **45**, 1771.
80. X.-H. Chen, X.-Y. Xu, H. Liu, L.-F. Cun and L.-Z. Gong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 14802.
81. Ch. S. Reddy and A. Nagaraj, *Heterocycl. Commun.*, 2007, **13**, 67.
82. R. Ghorbani-Vaghei and S. M. Malaekhepoor, *Org. Prep. Proced. Int.*, 2010, **42**, 175.
83. S. K. Kundu, S. Islam, A. Hajra and A. Majee, *Russ. J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **46**, 126.

